

TEACHING ENGLISH TO LEARNERS AT THE A2 LEVEL THROUGH AUTHENTIC DIALOGUES

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One of the primary benefits of conversations is the exposure to real-world language usage. Authentic dialogues have a great communicative value in contemporary English language instruction, which gives them a new significance and character. Through a theoretical framework that explains English language traits, the paper seeks to uncover novel approaches to utilize actual dialogues. One of the primary benefits of conversations is the exposure to real-world language usage. Authentic dialogues have a new meaning and quality in contemporary English language instruction, and they have substantial communicative value. Through a theoretical framework that explains English language traits, the essay seeks to uncover novel applications of actual dialogues. In non-teaching contexts that foster genuine interaction, English language learners frequently do not engage in spontaneous discussions. Learners can talk in English in a variety of contexts, including casual conversations and corporate meetings, when the language is utilized in everyday interactions. This covers aspects of creating genuine discussion, its methods, and assessment that are commonly omitted from conventional language textbooks. It is clear from observations that encouraging oral engagement and creating real communication are given less attention in English language training when developing socio-cultural and communicative competencies. There is a lack of clarity regarding the communicative approach in English language teaching as well as the methods and techniques that constitute authentic oral interaction, and the development of oral interactions for some classroom activities makes it difficult to create meaningful opportunities. According to research on English language methodology, teachers can address concerns about their familiarity with dialogue pedagogy, whether the requirements improve language proficiency in authentic conversations, and how to support their dialogue approach by using authentic dialogues to teach language. Results show that teaching strategies for learning original dialogues help students become more critical thinkers and problem solvers,

as well as active learners who are encouraged to take ownership of their education. Furthermore, textbooks do not engage students as much as fictional texts or conversations since they usually repeat pre-written texts and dialogues and do not always present real-world examples of spoken language. Sometimes, students' freedom of expression is restricted by the pre-written dialogues found in textbooks, which prevent them from discussing real-life occurrences. Furthermore, it is difficult to promote sincere connection and a free exchange of ideas when there are unfinished concepts and clarifying questions in the writings. Therefore, it should be emphasized that investigating the theoretical foundations of the creation of authentic dialogues and implementing them are essential steps in resolving this problem. Numerous studies were carried out and several scholarly publications were produced in relation to the thesis project[8;52-55pp]. Professors D. Ismayilova M. Gaziyeva , and N. Valiyeva have written enough academic works regarding the role that dialogues play in the local development of English communication abilities. T. Pimenova , S. Vladimirovna , and D. Sevostyaniov . The techniques employed by J. Haberman , P. Fiere , and others are little documented. J. Richardz was kept. They talked about the psychological and pedagogical study of real-world communication conversations and looked at linguistic characteristics of the communicative approach, the use of dialogues in a real-world setting, and features basic characteristics, the communicative approach, and the tactic of employing conversations in a genuine setting. Research that enables one to assess originality in English communication in current scientific-methodical literature is still lacking, as is the challenge of establishing the objectivity of oral speech and speech behaviour in communication circumstances[3;78].

English language learners who can talk critically and independently in conversations, integrate their thoughts with the world around them, approach challenges creatively, and solve difficulties are needed in today's fast evolving culture. One of the main objectives for this is the development of communicative competence as a variable model in a new change to the English teaching process. Authenticity, or the use of innovative methods, is one of the most effective ways to create genuine communication in English and has emerged as the most distinctive communication strategy [6;15]. According to B. Tomlins, effective actual dialogues should motivate students to study new information and get them ready for genuine conversations with people outside the audience. It is often recognized that studying other languages has long involved the usage of original resources. At the end of the 19th century, linguists emphasized the advantages of consistently use authentic texts in their research [2;43-

46pp]. A speech process arises as a result of the language's laws, and language learners' cognitive, emotive, and creative growth is greatly impacted by the linguistic didactic principles of employing authentic English dialogues. It's critical to precisely process words, select appropriate terminology, and articulate them in accordance with pronunciation norms when speaking, particularly during dialogues. [4;21-23pp] . S. Bruning , M. Dials , and A. Shirka contend that another language element of communication abilities is semantic competence. It entails comprehending the meaning of grammatical devices and structures, focusing on pragmatic semantics, making links between language units and grammatical semantics, and comprehending word meaning in context during conversations. In order to develop semantic competence, real conversations are analysed from a socio-pragmatic competence[7;25-31pp] . An good discussion usually consists of four essential components: specifications, summary, concise parts, and symmetry For this, dialogues are used in the following ways:

- 1) Dialogue 1: high degree of informality, equality and effectiveness
- 2) Dialogue 2: casual conversations, business calls, and citations.
- 3) Dialogue 3: thank-you, formal, ironic, and serious conversations.
- 4) Dialogue 4: formal, ceremonial, referential, and individual introduction.

Symmetry. In real communication, the symmetry of the discourse dictates the balance of each partner's words. All participants in the conversation should talk simultaneously.

Short sections. According to Alex Pattakos , brief excerpts from actual conversations show the volume of words spoken simultaneously. Acronyms require the speaker to pause frequently while they wait for their turn to speak and listen, or the listener to interrupt frequently in order to retain important information in a concise manner. Quick breaks can be helpful in this case[1;52-55pp].

Description. When utilizing genuine dialogues as the most efficient method of problem solving, scholars note on how important it is to recognize and characterize the main difficulties and problems. Both parties are able to reach an acceptable conclusion and generate the chance to build an action plan that benefits them both by means of communication, achieving an agreement, resolving conflicts or grievances, and clearly stating issues. Asking clarifying questions to determine the characteristics of the partner's main concerns in the conversation, as well as any other suggestions, increases the chances of success at this stage [5;99-103pp].

It became clear that learning does not often use authentic dialogues. The cause was explained by the very basic treatment of this subject in the English

language teaching curriculum. It was found that when planning and executing the original talks, a number of psychological factors are ignored. Self-assurance, comfort, creativity, and motivation are underrepresented. Lack of knowledge about the concept of authentic dialogue and the few tools and resources available for its use in education are further contributing factors. The teachers' lack of knowledge on the framework of meaningful communication was evident in their interview responses. Notably, the program did not provide any training on how to create dialogue. It was believed that educators needed current training on this subject for English language teachers.

Giving pupils samples of fiction with unique dialogue is another methodological challenge. The linguistic characteristics and original structure of this kind of dialogue are known to be more pronounced in fiction. The guidelines for identifying starts, repeats, ellipses, and spaces are more broadly applied here. The selection of fiction was determined by the requirements, and the selection of genuine literary dialogues clarified the features of their delivery.

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